

Synthesis and Biological Studies of α -Aryl-*N*-(4-methylthio/phenylthiophenyl)nitrones

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Several differently substituted α -aryl-*N*-(4-methylthio/phenylthiophenyl)nitrones have been synthesised and characterised. The antibacterial activity of some of these compounds are tested against several gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

In continuation of our work on the chemistry of nitrones¹, we got interested in the synthesis of sulphur containing nitrones with the expectation that the introduction of sulphur moiety may broaden or potentiate the biological activity of the nitrones². With this aim, several hitherto unknown 2/4-substituted- α -aryl-*N*-(4-methylthio/phenylthiophenyl)nitrones (1a-o, 2a-f, 2h, 2j, 2k, 2m and 2n) have been synthesised by the condensation of differently substituted benzaldehydes with 4-methylthio- and 4-phenylthiophenylhydroxylamines. These phenylhydroxylamines were in turn prepared from the

clear that all the nitrones (1 and 2) have *trans*-

orientation around $\text{C}=\text{N}^+$. It is also evident that

in 1k and 2k where the α -aryl ring carries a C₂-hydroxyl group, the preferred conformation is X

1; R=Ph
2; R=Me

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| a; R ₁ =R ₂ =H | i; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =SPh |
| b; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =Me | j; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =S- <i>p</i> -tolyl |
| c; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =OMe | k; R ₁ =OH, R ₂ =H |
| d; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =Cl | l; R ₁ =OMe, R ₂ =H |
| e; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =NMe ₂ | m; R ₁ =Cl, R ₂ =H |
| f; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =SMe | n; R ₁ =NO ₂ , R ₂ =H |
| g; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =SO ₂ Me | o; R ₁ =SPh, R ₂ =H |
| h; R ₁ =H, R ₂ =NO ₂ | |

corresponding nitro compounds^{3,4}. Though both these hydroxylamines have not been reported so far, only 4-methylthiophenylhydroxylamine was isolated and characterised (m.p. 83–84°, ethanol; ¹H nmr δ 8.40 (dd, C₂ and C₆-H), 7.5 (d, C₃ and C₅-H), 2.55 (s, SMe), while 4-phenylthiophenylhydroxylamine was prepared *in situ* and used as such. The physical and ¹H nmr data of the nitrones are given in Table 1.

From the ¹H nmr data and from the fact that *ortho*-hydrogens of α -aryl ring would be deshielded when they are closer to the nitrone oxygen⁵, it is

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p °C	δ					Other ArH	Other H hydrogens
			α -H s	2,6, 2',6' d	3',5' d	3,5 d	Other		
1a	76	117–19	7.80	8.40	← 7.2–76 →			—	
b	77	104–06	7.80	8.30	← 7.2–7.65 →		2.45 (Me)		
c	79	100–02	7.80	8.35	← 6.95–7.65 →		3.90 (OMe)		
d	77	156–57	7.85	8.35	← 7.20–7.65 →		—		
e	78	157–59	7.85	8.30	← 7.20–7.70 →		3.05 (Me)		
f	79	160–62	7.85	8.30	← 7.20–7.70 →		2.55 (Me)		
g	86	177–78	8.00	8.50	← 7.20–7.70 →		3.10 (Me)		
h	76	159–61	8.00	8.50	← 7.40–8.3 →		—		
i	78	120–22	8.00	8.50	← 7.40–9.85 →		—		
j	78	131–33	8.00	8.45	← 7.30–7.85 →		2.40 (Me)		
k	77	126–28	8.00	7.40	← 6.80–7.80 →		12.60 (OH)		
l	76	94–96	8.50	9.70	← 6.90–7.85 →		3.90 (OMe)		
m	76	123–24	8.70	9.50	← 7.40–8.35 →		—		
n	80	108–11	8.20	9.0	← 7.40–8.35 →		—		
o	67	104–06	8.50	9.70	← 7.20–8.20 →		—		
2a	78	107–08	7.80	8.30	7.70 7.25 7.60	—	2.50 (Me)		
b	76	126–27	7.85	8.35	7.70 7.25 7.35	—	2.55 (SMe) 2.40 (ArMe)		
c	81	143–44	7.80	8.35	7.70 7.30 6.95	—	2.50 (SMe) 3.80 (OMe)		
d	76	136–37	7.90	8.35	7.70 7.30 7.45	—	2.50 (SMe)		
e	74	151–52	7.80	8.35	7.70 7.30 7.20	—	2.55 (SMe) 3.05 (NMe ₂)		
f	73	158–60	7.85	8.35	7.70 7.30 7.20	—	2.5 (SMe) (6H)		
h	74	141–42	8.05	8.55	7.70 7.30 8.30	—	2.55 (SMe)		
j	80	121–22	8.00	8.50	7.70 7.30 —	7.60 ^a	2.50 (SMe) 2.40 (ArMe)		
k	76	116–18	8.05	^b 7.70	7.20 7.40 ^b —		2.50 (SMe) 12.50 (OH)		
m	68	117–19	8.65	9.30 ^a	7.70 7.40 8.10(C ₃ -H), 7.50 ^c -7.80 (C ₄ -C ₅ H)		2.55 (SMe)		
n	67	93–94	8.60	9.40 ^a	7.70 7.30 8.10d(C ₃ H), 7.60-7.80 (C ₄ -C ₅ H)		2.55 (SMe)		

^aC₂-H alone. ^bC₆-H merges with other aromatic hydrogen. ^cThis reference includes aryl H of *S-p*-tolyl group.

wherein the nitron oxygen is involved in hydrogen bonding leaving the C₆-H unaffected. All other nitrones prefer a conformation Y, where the interaction between C₂-substituent of α -aryl ring and the nitron oxygen is avoided, leaving the C₆-H to experience the entire deshielding effect of the nitron oxygen.

X

Y

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial activity of some of the compounds of series 1 viz 1c¹, 1d, 1e, 1f, 1h, 1j, 1k, 1l, 1m and 1n were tested against six gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus aureus*, *Klasiella aerogenes*, *Shigella flexneri*, *Salmonella typhi* 'H' and *Proteus miroabilis*. The compounds of series 2 were tested against former three microorganisms listed above, apart from *Staphylococcus albus*, *Psuedomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*. The antimicrobial activity was tested based on the disc diffusion method⁶. In this method, filter paper disc (6.25 mm dia) was sterilised at 140° and the compound (500 μ g/disc) in acetone was taken. The cultures were made in nutrient agar plate and the discs were placed on the culture-agar layer. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37°. For each compound, the diameter of the circular areas of inhibition were plotted against the logarithms of the concentration of the sulphur nitron used for these experiments.

While the nitron 1l has good response (zone of inhibition, 11 mm) towards both *Staphylococcus aureus* (zone of inhibition, 11 mm) and *S. flexneri* (9 mm), the nitrones 1e (10 mm) and 1f (9 mm) have good response towards *Staphylococcus aureus*. Other nitrones show less to moderate activity (2–8 mm) towards other microorganisms tested. In the series 2, except *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus aureus*, all other microorganisms show good response to at least one of the nitrones tested. Thus 2f (12 mm) is very active against *S. albus*, 2h (12 mm) against *P. aerogenosa*, 2n (12 mm) against *E. coli* and 2e (16 mm) against *K. aerogens*. Thus

the 4-methylthio group at *N*-aryl ring seems to be more active against bacteria than a 4-phenylthio group in the same position.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (95% EtOH) were on a Philips PU 8800 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R32 spectrometer (90 Hz) with TMS as internal standard.

4-Phenylthionitrobenzene was prepared from benzenethiol and 4-chloronitrobenzene following the reported procedure⁸, while 4-methylthionitrobenzene was prepared by methylation of 4-nitrothiophenol⁴.

α -Aryl-N-(4-methylthio/phenylthiophenyl) nitrone (1 and 2). **General procedure:** The corresponding nitro compound (20 mmol) was reduced with zinc (4 g) and ammonium chloride (2 g) in warm ethanol (60 ml) by the usual method⁷. The concentrated chloroform extract of this hydroxylamine (20 ml) was added with a clear solution of aromatic aldehyde (15 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml) with stirring, and the mixture was kept at 60° for 1 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: 1a $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N) and 1 070 cm⁻¹ (N-O), $\lambda_{\max}$ 202, 251 and 324 nm; 2a $\nu_{\max}$ 1 560 (C=N) and 1 065 (N-O), $\lambda_{\max}$ 203, 255 and 334 nm.

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References

1. S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, P. MANISANKAR and N. ARUMUGAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 454; S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, P. MANISANKAR, M. PALANIANDAVAR and N. ARUMUGAM, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1982, 7, 346; D. X. WEST, S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, P. MANISANKAR, M. PALANIANDAVAR and N. ARUMUGAM, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1983, 8, 317; N. ARUMUGAM, P. MANISANKAR, S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN and D. A. WILSON, *Org. Magn. Reson.*, 1984, 22, 592; 1985, 23, 246; S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, P. MANISANKAR, R. RAMACHANDRAN and N. ARUMUGAM, *Sulfur Lett.*, 1984, 2, 23; S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, P. MANISANKAR, P. JEYARAM and N. ARUMUGAM, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1985, 59, 369; M. THENMOZHI, S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, P. BALAKRISHNAN and D. W. BOYKIN, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1986, 340; S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, K. RAVICHANDRAN, A. PONNUSAMY S. MUTHUSUBRAMANIAN and V. MAHENDRAN, *Phosphorus Sulfur*, 1992, 66, 165; S. SIVASUBRAMANIAN, K. RAVICHANDRAN, S. MUTHUSUBRAMANIAN, A. C. CHANDRA and V. MAHENDRAN, *Sulfur Lett.*, 1992, 14, 53.
2. W. KEIEGEL, *Pharmazie*, 1977, 32, 643.
3. H. V. HODGSON and E. V. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1634.
4. C. C. PRICE and G. W. STACH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 498.
5. K. KOYANO and H. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, 42, 3306.
6. F. J. BAKER, 'Handbook of Bacteriological Technique', Butterworths, London, 1967; R. CRUICKSHANK, 'Medical Microbiology', Edinburg, Kingston, 1974; H. C. CHOPRA "Text Book of Medical Microbiology", New Delhi, 1985, p. 81.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1956, p. 629.